

BRIGHT SPACE

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

Deliverable D3.1: Preliminary report on the impact on Technology, Structural change and Demand side processes

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DATE OF APPROVAL:	25.04.2024
APPROVED BY PROJECT COORDINATOR:	Marc Mueller (WR)
DATE OF APPROVAL:	26.04.2024
CALL	Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the Green Deal
WORK PROGRAMME Topic ID	EU agriculture within a safe and just operating space and planetary boundaries HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-12
PROJECT WEB SITE:	https://brightspace-project.eu/

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History of changes

Version	Publication date	Changes	Who
0.1	11.04.2024	Draft Version	Hugo Storm
0.2	17.04.2024	Internal Review	Olaf Heidelberg
0.3	19.04.2024	Internal Review	Birgit Müller
0.4	24.04.2024	Internal Review	Anne Maréchal
1.1	25.04.2024	Consolidation/Approval	Hugo Storm
1.2	26.04.2024	Approval	Marc Mueller

Citation

Storm, H. & Aladesuru, D.T. & Kuhn, T. & Cechura, L. & Zakova Kroupova, Z. & Curtiss, J. & Sckokai, P. & Tiboldo, G. & Castellari, E. & Moro, D. & Podmaniczky, L. & Balázs, K. & Neuenfeldt, S. & Bouamra-Mechemache, Z. & Feenstra, N. & Gehrke, E. & Ferrer Pérez, H. (2024). Deliverable D3.1 (D5). Preliminary report on the impact on Technology, Structural change and Demand side processes. BrightSpace Horizon Europe project, GA Nr. 101060075.

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ACRONYMS

CAPRI	Common Agricultural Policy Regional Impact Analysis
CGE	Computable General Equilibrium
CITA	Centro de Investigación y Tecnología Agroalimentaria, Spain
CZU	Czech University of Life Sciences, Prague
ECAMPA	Economic Assessment of GHG mitigation policy options for EU agriculture
EU	European Union
FADN	Farm Accounting Data Network
FaSC	Farm Structural Change
FISC	Field Structural Change
FLW	Food loss and waste
FSS	EU Farm Structural Survey
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
GHGEs	Greenhouse Gas Emissions
GM	Genetically Modified
GMOs	Genetically Modified Organisms
HBS	Household Budget Survey

IACS	Integrated Administration and Control System
INRAE	Institut national de la recherche agronomique (France's National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment); France
M36; M18	Month 36; Month 18
MAGNET	Modular Applied General Equilibrium Tool
N2O	Nitrous Oxide
NGTs	New Genomic Techniques
OFTU	On-Farm Technology Usage
PLAB	Planslab Ltd., Hungary
R&D	Research and Development
SJ	Safe and Just
SJOS	Safe and Just Operating Space
Thuenen	Johann Heinrich von Thuenen-Institut (Thuenen Institute), Germany
UBO	University of Bonn, Germany
UCSC	Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (Catholic University of the Sacred Heart), Italy
UK	United Kingdom
USA	United States of America
USD	United States Dollars
WP	Work Package
WR	Wageningen Research, Netherlands
WU	Wageningen University, Netherlands

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents preliminary work from Work Package (WP) 3. The WP aims to provide and improve basic understanding of non-policy processes relevant to Safe and Just Operating Space (SJOS) outcomes. The WP takes an ex-post perspective to study the relationships of interest. This provides the basis for ex-ante modelling activities within BrightSpace. Specifically, WP3 aims to systematically collect the available empirical knowledge of relevant non-policy processes, identify research gaps, and address these gaps through novel empirical analysis. It covers non-policy processes on the supply as well as on the demand side.

The preliminary deliverable presents completed and planned activities relating, on the supply side, to on-farm technology usage, farm structural change, farming intensity and field structural change. Those are tasks 3.1 and 3.2. The deliverable also reports completed activities and planned work for task 3.3 Consumer diets/preferences/waste reflecting the demand side processes addressed in the WP.

Within each chapter, we first provide the results of a systematic literature review to collect empirical evidence of how the considered process links to the outcome of different SJ dimensions. This literature review also identifies major research gaps where empirical knowledge is lacking to determine the importance of a process for an SJ dimension or where empirical quantification is lacking to provide sufficient information to model the relationship. Secondly, in each section, we present the empirical activities we aim to conduct within the second half of WP3. Thirdly, we discuss how empirical knowledge of the considered processes can be included in ex-ante models, identifying modelling needs and possible modelling interfaces.

The literature review on the linkages between the SJOS and agricultural production decisions provide guidance and prioritization for future modelling and further research activities. Our findings reveal substantial knowledge on the relationship between on-farm technology usage, farm and field structural change, consumer preferences, and waste with the thematic areas of the EU SJOS. The literature review also identifies the need for more empirical work to generate useful estimates that can be used to quantify and model the identified relationships in ex-ante models. The planned activities described under 'intended work' for the second half of the WP3 are open to modification based on the project development during the implementation of the activities.

1. INTRODUCTION

Deliverable 3.1 captures the research activities of Work Package 3 (WP3). WP3 aims to provide and improve our basic understanding of non-policy processes relevant to Safe and Just Operating Space (SJOS) outcomes by taking an ex-post perspective to study relationships of interest. On the supply side, the WP looks at relationship to SJOS outcomes of on-farm technology usage, farm structural change and field structural change. On the demand side; consumer diets, preferences and food waste. The WP aims to systematically collect the available empirical knowledge of relevant non-policy processes in the scientific literature, identify research gaps, and address these gaps through novel empirical analysis. These activities will provide useful knowledge, quantification parameters and areas for future consideration for ex-ante policy modelling work in the BrightSpace project.

This deliverable is the first deliverable of WP3; it is a preliminary deliverable presenting the work done in the WP within the first 18 months of the project. During this time, the main activities include systematic literature review and identifying possible interfaces to ex-ante models. The deliverable is structured to present the results of these activities around the three categories of non-policy processes addressed within WP3. *Task 3.1 Supply side processes: Technology* (chapter 2), *Task 3.2 Supply side: Structural change* (chapter 3), and *Task 3.3 Demand side: Consumer diets / preferences / waste* (chapter 4). Within each chapter, we first provide the results of a systematic literature review that aims to collect existing empirical evidence of how the considered process links to the different Safe and Just (SJ) dimensions. This literature review also aims to identify major research gaps in terms of where empirical knowledge is lacking either to determine the importance of a process for an SJ dimension or where empirical quantification is lacking in order to provide sufficient information to model the relationship. Secondly, in each section, we present the empirical activities we intend to conduct during the second half of WP3 (i.e., until M36). Thirdly, we discuss how empirical knowledge of the considered processes can be included in ex-ante models, identifying modelling needs and possible modelling interfaces.

Intended activities described within each task chapter represent the intention of the work we aim to conduct. The actual activities might deviate from this description depending on the project needs and developments.

2. TASK 3.1 SUPPLY SIDE: TECHNOLOGY (WP LEAD: CZU)

This task investigates adoption processes of existing farm technologies. In particular, it aims to improve our understanding what drives farmers adoption decisions. We synthesise existing knowledge in the literature but also tackle novel aspects for example the role of contract work as a way how new technologies come into the production process or to what extent field size structure matters for adoption decision. We also study secondary effects, such as structural/behavioural changes induced by technology adoption, which can have important consequences for technologies SJOS outcomes but are hardly studied empirically. Crucially we also assess and quantify how technology adoption impact varies SJOS outcomes at varies scales. An understanding of the driving forces of adoption processes and their impact in SJOS outcomes to inform ex-ante modelling, but also an important bases to assess diffusion of novel technologies in WP8.

This section is structured as follows. Section 2.1 provides the results of a systematic literature review aiming to identify how on-farm technology usage are related to the different SJOS dimensions. Section 2.2 presents the planned empirical activities within the task, and section 2.3 discusses of how the considered technologies can be considered in ex-ante models, what model interfaces, and what empirical knowledge is required.

2.1. Literature Review of existing empirical evidence

On-farm technology usage (OFTU) broadly describes processes and practices relating to soil- and crop management as well as the use of technologies like precision farming and biotechnologies. OFTU is central to agriculture production and is expected to impact many safe (Campbell et al. 2017; Xian et al. 2023) and just thematic areas. Considering the breadth of technologies used in agriculture, this review activity and the literature evidence presented is limited to selected important technologies in the EU: land management, machinery, biotechnology, precision or smart farming and organic farming.

The literature review follows a systematic procedure to find records relating OFTU to the minimum set of 12 thematic areas of environmental and social dimensions that are relevant for the EU agricultural system. The 12 thematic areas follow the dimension identified in WP1 (see table 1). Web of Science (WoS) is used as primary search database, in specific cases as supporting argumentation, additional documents are snowballed. Topic keywords for each umbrella category are based on the aspects we aim to cover within each category. Keywords for thematic areas are based on understanding of the SJOS thematic areas and control variables as specified in pioneer SJOS papers (O'Neill et al. 2018; Raworth 2012; Rockström et al. 2009; Steffen et al. 2015). These keywords and their combinations to form search queries are presented in Appendix 1, subsections 8.1, 8.2, 8.3 and 8.4. From the search outcomes, only published, peer-reviewed, accessible, English articles are considered. Among these, screening and selection of relevant records is conducted in two stages. Firstly, titles and abstracts are screened to assess their relevance. Secondly, eligible studies are selected and considered in the review based on identified findings of interest in the full text. While the regional focus of the paper is the EU, we do not systematically exclude findings from other parts of the world as they may provide useful insight on possible impact mechanisms of a specific aspect on EU relevant SJOS thematic areas. The same procedure was applied in systematic literature reviews in section 3 and 4.

Table 1 Volume of evidence reviewed and cited for the relationships between agricultural production decision categories and the minimum set of thematic areas of environmental and social dimensions that are relevant for the EU agricultural system

Thematic areas		OFTU	FaSC	FiSC	Total
Environmental thematic area (Safe Operating Space)	Biodiversity	19	5	21	45
	Nutrient flows	11	5	8	24
	Aerosol loading	1	1	4	6
	Climate change	27	6	3	34
	Chemical pollution (novel entities)	10	1	1	12
	Land use	6	3	0	9
	Water use	0	1	0	1
Social thematic area (Just Operating Space)	Nutrition security	13	12	4	29
	Farm resilience	7	12	10	29
	Health	18	1	0	19
	Social equity	0	6	0	6
	Economy	6	0	0	6
	Total unique studies across thematic areas	104	52	49	203

Biodiversity

On-farm technologies have a strong impact on biodiversity. Many studies show that species richness decreases with the increasing intensity of agricultural management (Báldi & Faragó 2007; Collard et al. 2011; Frazão et al. 2017; García-Tomillo et al. 2017; Schwab et al. 2015; Toffoli & Rughetti 2017; Tuomisto et al. 2012; Wade et al. 2010). Notably, OFTU practices of large-scale monoculture, conventional tillage, intensive livestock systems and herbicide, insecticide, and fertilizer application tend to reduce levels of species richness. In contrast, crop diversification, organic farming, precision agriculture, biotechnology, and agroforestry are considered to be mitigating technologies for biodiversity loss (Beaumelle et al. 2023; Eynade et al. 2021; Goded et al. 2018; Kholilah et al. 2019; Schwab et al. 2015).

The use of biotechnology in agriculture has the potential to conserve natural ecosystems and genetic resources by reducing the requirements for crop protection chemicals, artificial fertilizers, tillage, and irrigation (Hansson & Joelsson 2013; Mannion 1998). However, biofortification and other methods of genetic engineering applied in modern agriculture could also pose risks to biodiversity (Hansson & Joelsson 2013; Johns & Eyzaguirre 2007). The protection of biodiversity in organic systems occurs through general effects attributable to a more varied presence of plant species and animals and through specific effects, such as a greater protection of pollinating insects (Calabro & Vieri 2024).

Organic management increases the abundance of organisms and species richness (Seufert & Ramankutty 2017). Advantages of organic farming are found to be higher in homogenous landscapes (Diame et al. 2015; Goded et al. 2018). Furthermore, organic farming has a stronger effect on biodiversity in arable systems than in grassland systems and a stronger impact within individual fields than at the farm scale (Eyinade et al. 2021). Lastly, Tschardt et al. (2021) summarized that organic/conventional farming is less important than field structure.

Nutrient Flows

The outcome of our review identifies that land management practices such as fertilization can impact nutrient flows through contribution to higher nitrate concentrations and nitrate leaching. Intensive agricultural production practices cause increased losses of applied N (Noor & Tejada Moral 2017). Crop diversification, rotation, and tillage also influence soil quality and, consequently, nutrient flow (Kiani et al. 2017; Nazaries et al. 2021). Different cropping systems, minimum-till or no-till practices can allow better uptake of nutrients from different depths of soil profile and restoration of nutrient balance by the N fixation process (Noor & Tejada Moral 2017). However, no-tillage systems can also pose a higher risk of N₂O emissions through low aeration (Rochette et al. 2008). Employing catch and cover crops can reduce the level of reactive N in the topsoil (Scialabba & Müller-Lindenlauf 2010). Additionally, controlled traffic farming reducing soil compaction can lower N fertilizer inputs (Hussein et al. 2021) and the consequent nutrient flow can be influenced by biotechnological options (Tesfahun & Yildiz 2018).

Various studies compare organic and conventional farming with respect to different aspects of nutrient flows in different contexts (Biernat et al. 2020; Calabro & Vieri 2024; Dalgaard et al. 2006; van Diepeningen et al. 2006; Maltais-Landry et al. 2019). Succinctly put, the impact of organic farming on nutrient flows seems to be mixed and depends on a broad range of production, soil and weather conditions (Scialabba & Müller-Lindenlauf 2010).

Climate Change, Chemical Pollution and Aerosol Loading

A wide range of alternative management practices are available to reduce GHG emissions and mitigate climate change. Such practices include 1) methane reduction technologies and feeding practices as well as keeping of specific breeds in livestock production (Scialabba & Müller-Lindenlauf 2010)¹, 2) agroforestry systems (Menichetti et al. 2020), 3) improving crop rotation (Guardia et al. 2016; Plaza-Bonilla et al. 2018), 4) minimum tillage and no-tillage cultivations (Chaplot et al. 2012; Dendoncker et al. 2004; Dyer & Desjardins 2003; Kragt et al. 2012; Sørensen et al. 2014; VandenBygaart 2016; West & Marland 2002) 5) employing enhanced efficiency fertilizers (Giltrap et al. 2010; Pathak & Wassmann 2007), 6) precision/smart farming technologies, 7) using low carbon farm machinery (Dendoncker et al. 2004), and 8) organic farming (Frank et al. 2010; Moudry et al. 2013; Necpalova et al. 2018).

The highest source of GHG emissions in conventional crop production is soil N₂O emission which can be reduced using nitrification inhibitors (Hargreaves et al. 2021; Ortiz et al. 2008) or slow-release fertilizers (Tuomisto et al. 2012). Minimum tillage and no-tillage could also lower GHG emissions however, this reduction is crop and site specific (Sørensen et al. 2014). Organic farming is considered to have considerably lower GHG emissions than comparable conventional systems when measured per area, although in some systems this benefit is lost when measured per ton of production, depending on yield differences (Bos et al. 2014; Dalgaard et al. 2006; Flessa et al. 2002; Meemken &

¹ Methane emissions from animal production represent a large share of total agricultural GHG emissions and technologies and management practices to reduce methane emissions are covered in several studies, although not necessarily covered by the literature review e.g., because they were published as project reports (e.g., the ECAMPA report, Pérez-Dominguez et al. (2020)) or not in English language (e.g. Lesschen et al. (2020) for a Dutch case)

Qaim 2018; Venkat 2012). Furthermore, Muller et al. (2016) highlighted evidence for higher levels of carbon sequestration in organic systems compared to conventional ones. However, the possible expansion of organic farming to replace conventional one keeping the current production levels could only be achieved through a higher availability of lands and increased use of manure with an inevitable increase in methane emissions (Calabro & Vieri 2024).

Chemical pollution encompasses a wide range of substances, including those from the application of synthetic pesticides and fertilizers for crop production and protection, as well as use of antibiotics for animal health management. Some identified technologies for this are organic farming (Edwards-Jones & Howells 2001; Pérez-Méndez et al. 2023), biotechnologies (Paoletti & Pimentel 2000) and precision/smart farming (Stoian et al. 2022). In organic farming, chemical pesticides, chemical fertilizers, growth hormones, antibiotics and GM organisms are strongly restricted or prohibited (Puech et al. 2014) and hence are relevant technology for the chemical pollution thematic area. However, the lower persistence of organic insecticides compared to synthetic ones usually leads to their more frequent use which also needs to be accounted for (Edwards-Jones & Howells 2001). Extended crop rotations and the use of resistant varieties are another important mechanism to reduce insecticide use (Pimentel et al. 1993).

Biotechnologies are helpful through development of crops with heavy metal tolerance (Elango et al. 2022) and crops resistant to pathogens (Schaak et al. 2021) that allow a reduction in the use of chemicals like insecticides and fungicides in crop production (Paoletti & Pimentel 2000). Nonetheless, there are also environmental concerns associated with the utilization of GMOs in agriculture (Hansson & Joelsson 2013).

For aerosol loading, just one relevant study that examines aerosol loading (specifically matter emission) shows that tractors equipped with the most recent emissions savings technologies can reduce matter emission (Bacenetti et al. 2018).

Land Use

Intensification, modernization, and specialization of agriculture have important consequences for land cover and land use change (Mottet et al. 2006), extending to deforestation as well as farmland abandonment (García-Ruiz & Lana-Renault 2011). The impact of investments in agricultural technologies on land productivity and the resulting expansion of agricultural areas at the cost of forest areas and/or other previously unproductive pristine areas (Kaimowitz & Angelsen 2001) has been empirically shown in non-European Union countries (e.g., in Brazil (Rocha et al. 2019). However, empirical research on the impact of agricultural technology use such as mechanization and innovations on land use change in EU countries is lacking in the reviewed literature. Organic farming requires more land to compensate for the lower yields (Kirchmann 2019; Meemken & Qaim 2018) and implies additional land use and land cover change when additional organic farming is not linked to demand side changes.

Nutrition Security

Similar to land use the main mechanism of how OFTU could impact nutrition security is indirectly via its effects on yields and hence of total available supply of calories produced. This could impact food prices and hence affordability. Technologies might also change relative production costs for different food categories and hence impact relative cost for different food products with different health benefits (e.g., technology might reduce relative costs for nutrient or vitamin rich costs). For capturing relative production costs, it is important to address yield effects differentiated by crop (-categories). The observably lower yields in organic farming give reason for concern when considering the growing demand for food (Kirchmann 2019). According to Stoian et al. (2022), organic farming lowers production compared to intensive agriculture. Upscaling organic farming could lead to disruptions in food security and more widespread environmental degradation (Connor 2021). However, research

shows that changes on the demand side can compensate for some shortcomings (Muller et al. 2017). Contrarily, biotechnology (Bearth et al. 2022; Santaniello 2005; Wu et al. 2014) or the adoption of precision farming technologies (Figiel 2022; Mizik 2023; Reis et al. 2020) represent potential solutions to food security problems.

The impact of organic farming and biotechnologies is crop- and site-specific. Summarizing results of three meta-analysis on crop yields, Meemken & Qaim (2018) identify lower yields of organic farming but with considerable differences across different crops. Genetic engineering is found to increase the global supply of crops such as maize and soybean (Scheitrum et al. 2020) partly caused by yield gains (Meemken & Qaim 2018), but at potentially higher production cost. With the development of new plant breeding technologies (NPBTs), the possibilities of allowed use of biotechnology in organic agriculture could reduce the food security risks that are caused by scaling up organic farming (Purnhagen et al. 2021).

Farm Resilience and Economy

When examining OFTU impacts on farm resilience, assessing yield effects of technology appears once more as one of the most relevant indirect aspects. Further aspects are investment needs and how (novel) technologies will affect production costs. Certain farming systems, such as organic, might also allow farmers to realize higher prices if consumers are willing to pay a price premium and if adequate marketing and labelling regulations are in place.

Non-European studies found out that the adoption of soil fertility conserving technologies and improved agronomic practices (Hörner & Wollni 2021), mechanization of smallholder farming systems (Adu-Baffour et al. 2019), and adoption of biotechnologies (Ali & Abdulai 2010) contributed to higher household income and poverty reduction. Also, organic farming can improve the income of smallholder farmers (Malek et al. 2019; Ramankutty et al. 2019), especially due to the price premium on certified organic products and reduced input costs (Panneerselvam et al. 2010). However, the effect on poverty reduction is not clear. A general observation is that farm mechanization can compensate for labor scarcity, which can be a major constraint in some farming systems (Kandpal et al. 2022).

The literature review on energy access which is covered in the thematic area economy reveals that the main on-farm technologies that can influence energy access are agricultural waste management (i.e., waste processing in biogas plants) and biotechnologies. Anaerobic digestion of farm residues (e.g., manure and slurry) is expected to be an efficient and ecologically sustainable approach to renewable energy production (Blumenstein et al. 2018; Siegmeier et al. 2015; Swindal et al. 2010). Recent advances in genetic engineering also allow farmers to use less energy on farms (Hansson & Joelsson 2013), to increase agricultural land productivity and consequently increase the amount of land available for biofuels (Zilberman et al. 2013). This reduces the costs of producing biofuels, which is a widely recognized alternative to fossil fuels (Debnath et al. 2019). However, the reviewed literature does not provide precise measure of the impact of on-farm technology on energy access.

Health

On-farm technologies impacts health in various ways. Land management decisions can affect air and water quality (Thorburn & Wilkinson 2013). Excessive use of pesticides and fertilizers can lead to contamination of air, water, soil and food with adverse impacts on both food security and food safety (Elango et al. 2022). Intensive land cultivation exerts a high influence on water quality (Gagliardi & Pettigrove 2013), primarily due to their increased reliance on pesticides (Mack et al. 2023) and fertilizers. Research reports that organic farming has lower pesticide residues compared to conventional production (Lotter 2003) and that other unhealthy components such as nitrates and cadmium are lower (Lotter 2003; Meemken & Qaim 2018).

Crop protection practices may affect human health also through the risk of infectious diseases, bacterial infections, and parasitic diseases. More specifically, the use of synthetic agricultural fungicides poses risk of antimicrobial resistance (Ratnadass & Sester 2023). Organic farming, which only allows the use of antibiotics to save the life of animals, reduces the risk of antibiotic resistance (Lotter 2003). Regarding nutritionally desirable components, the results are mixed (Beltrán-González et al. 2008; Meemken & Qaim 2018; Pérez-López et al. 2007).

Although biotechnology is also discussed as a potential threat to the environment and to human health, several authors (Hansson & Joelsson 2013; Qaim 2009; Yang & Chen 2016) argue that agricultural biotechnology can positively affect human health by decreasing exposure to pesticides, improving the nutritional value of food, and by producing pharmaceuticals more efficiently. Apart from pollutants, mechanization poses a threat to the health of agricultural workers, particularly through the risk of injuries (Angioloni et al. 2020) or through noise and vibration (Butkus & Vasiliauskas 2018; De Temmerman et al. 2004).

Through precision farming, organic farming, and biotechnologies, agricultural producers can mitigate the negative impacts of agricultural production on human health. For example, (Kouser & Qaim 2011) revealed that the production of genetically modified cotton in India yielded a 70% reduction in the most hazardous pesticides to human health. This is further supported by evidence of health care cost savings due to genetically modified eggplant technology (Krishna & Qaim 2008). With respect to the New Plant Breeding Technologies, there are several promising applications with improved food and feed quality such as lettuce with increased vitamin C content, wheat with lower gluten content or oilseed rape with improved fatty acid composition (Purnhagen & Wessler 2021).

2.2. Empirical work (planned) to create new empirical evidence

2.2.1. Technology adoption – Organic farming

Intended work: Conversion to organic farming requires significant structural adjustments at different levels of the farming system, involving a fundamental change in production processes, management practices, and market positioning. These complex structural adjustments are associated with high conversion costs, uncertainties, as well as opportunity costs. The structural characteristics (proximity) of the farms (before and after conversion) and their environment (structural synergies) can significantly influence the comparative costs and challenges associated with organic conversion. Using the EU farm panel data (FADN) over the period 2010-2020, the analysis of organic conversion will focus on the effects of farm structural and economic heterogeneity as well as their development over time. To complement this analysis of structural fixed effects on organic farming adoption, we plan to conduct two comparative case studies using the National Agricultural Census data for Germany and the Czech Republic. These case studies will focus on selected production specializations (farm types). As an alternative approach, we aim to explore the potential of analysing conversion rates specific to different farm types at the EU NUTS2 regional level using EU Farm Structural Survey (FSS) data from 2010 and 2020, or FADN data depending on the representativeness of the conversion rates. This analysis would explore the impact of regional farm structure, demographic factors, sectoral structures as well as variations in policy support and market demand.

2.2.2. Estimation of the economic impact of the various considered technologies

Intended work: We aim to use micro-level data (FADN) to estimate the economic impact of various considered technologies covered by the data (e.g., organic farming) using transformation model and

investigate the process (or the outcome of the process) related to SJOS outcomes. In particular, we aim to provide empirical information for parametrization of those technologies in terms of production characteristics (such as production elasticities, input and output shadow shares), productivity and yield effects, costs and impacts of safe outcomes. We also aim to study the role of contract work as a way how new technologies come into the production process.

2.3. Interfaces to ex-ante models

OFTU can affect SJOS outcomes either via production intensity or via its effect on land productivity and hence yield (figure 1). OFTU mainly impacts the thematic areas biodiversity, nutrient flows, chemical pollution, climate change, and aerosol loading by influencing agricultural management intensities. Notably, technologies can lead to intensification of production but can also enable less intensive production systems (e.g., via precision agriculture or organic farming). Also, technologies and production intensity can in principle impact human health, however, their exact impact in European countries is not provided by the reviewed studies. By impacting yields and land productivity OFTU determines land demand for agricultural production. This in turn impacts nutrition security and farm resilience. We find no evidence of impact on water use and social equity.

Agricultural policy modelling that seeks to capture OFTU impact on the SJOS therefore primarily needs to i) assess how technology impacts farming intensity or production systems and how it affects yields, (land) productivity and farm income opportunities (in respect to associated just outcomes). Further, ii) we need to be able to assess how these different levels of intensity or production systems affect SJOS outcomes. For i), the key challenge is to identify the most relevant technologies and to provide an empirical parameterization of their production effects and costs, preferably distinguishing required investments, fixed, and variable costs at sufficient level of detail. For many technologies, data does not exist to parametrize production functions in large-scale models as these technologies are currently not sufficiently spread in general or in the EU. Furthermore, to reflect the possibilities of technology upscaling (moving from the situation of current negligible use to a massive uptake), the drivers of technology adoption should be investigated and ideally also endogenized in the models. Concerning biotechnologies, adoption depends significantly on the R&D transfer supported or driven by regulatory approval. Assumptions of regulatory approval are thus important drivers of biotechnology adoption that should be included in the models. Contrary to organic farming, where cost structures can be obtained for parametrization of the production functions, at least in some of the EU member state countries, parameterization of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) / new genomic techniques (NGTs) would need to be done based on data from outside of the EU.

For ii), models need to be able to quantify how farming intensities and different production systems relate to safe outcomes: Biodiversity, Nutrient flows, Chemical pollution, Climate Change, Aerosol loading and relevant just outcomes, e.g., Health. Existing policy models are already quite detailed in this respect but with a huge variation of the potential SJOS-related outcomes that can be modelled, depending on the scope of the model. In general, the simulation models can either directly calculate indicators for SJOS outcomes as endogenous variables or estimate indicators post-model after the actual modelling. An example of the former is GHG emissions in the farm-level model FarmDyn (Britz et al. 2021), which are included as endogenous variables and can be directly included in the optimization process, e.g., for an emission cap. In the same model, biodiversity indicators, for instance, are calculated based on a range of endogenous variables like land allocation after the model was executed. If the SJOS impacts are directly linked to standard input-output coefficients, information on the impact of new technologies on these coefficients is sufficient. However, technologies which cause changes in the bio-physical properties of farming activities require additional data, for example, in the case of feed additives for lowering methane emissions.

Ultimately, it is required to prioritize technologies according to their potential on productivity and farming systems and to provide empirical information for parametrization of those technologies in terms of yield effects, costs and impacts of safe outcomes.

Figure 1 Categorization of SJOS thematic areas according to the literature review findings on on-farm technology usage (OFTU).

3. TASK 3.2 SUPPLY SIDE: STRUCTURAL CHANGE (WP LEAD: UBO)

In this section, we consider aspects related to structural change and how they relate to SJOS outcomes. We distinguish farm structural change, changes in farming intensity, and changes in field level structural change. Farm structure is here understood as the composition and organization of an agricultural production unit. It includes elements such as the size of the land area and livestock herds, the labor force's characteristics, the means of production, and legal and organizational aspects of land tenure, farm management, and market access. Farming intensity refers to different levels of management intensity, for example, with respect to (pesticides/fertilizers) input use intensity. But it also includes aspects such as more or less intensive crop rotations. Field structural change covers aspects such as the composition of landscapes in which farms operate.

In section 3.1 we first present the results of a systematic literature review aiming to identify how these aspects are related to the different SJOS dimensions. Section 3.2 presents the planned empirical activities within the task, and section 3.3 presents a discussion of how the considered process can be considered in ex-ante models, what model interfaces, and what empirical knowledge is required.

3.1. Literature Review of existing empirical evidence

The literature review follows a systematic procedure to find records relating structural change to the minimum set of 12 thematic areas of environmental and social dimensions that are relevant for the EU agricultural system. Methodically the review follows the same approach as outline in section 2.1. In the following we present the results of the literature review in detail. Note that for review we consider aspect of Farm structural change (FaSC) and farming intensity jointly. These results are presented in section 3.1.1 while section 3.1.2 present the literature review on aspects related to field structural change (FiSC).

3.1.1. Farm Structural change and Farming Intensity

Biodiversity

The reviewed literature (see search queries in 8.1 and 8.3) offers evidence that farm sizes and specializations impact biodiversity. Smaller farm sizes are associated with enhanced biodiversity (Belfrage et al. 2015; Karlsson et al. 2022; Noack et al. 2022). Small-scale farms are associated with more varied landscapes, including semi-natural grasslands, which increase biodiversity (Karlsson et al. 2022). Similar to the discussion in section 5, the impact of farm size on biodiversity is mainly attributed to land cover simplification resulting from the farm size increase (Noack et al. 2022). The interplay of farm sizes and agricultural activities in relation to different farm specializations can generate varying biodiversity outcomes (Dabkiene et al. 2021; Karlsson et al. 2022; Smith et al. 2020). On the one hand, descriptive evidence shows, that Lithuanian medium-sized family farms as well as farms specializing in integrated field crops- and grazing livestock exhibit the most environmentally beneficial characteristics. In contrast, small and large farms as well as farms specializing solely in various crops, livestock and orchards are less beneficial (Dabkiene et al. 2021). Farms specializing in monogastric livestock are associated with less varied landscapes and suboptimal crop sequences which decreases biodiversity (Karlsson et al. 2022). A more holistic examination reveals that the integration of livestock and crop production fosters resilient native bird communities, particularly within landscapes dominated by intensive food production (Smith et al. 2020).

Overall, farms specializing in field crops, grazing livestock, or ruminants are found to be more beneficial compared to those specializing in horticulture or monogastric livestock. However, the reviewed literature primarily shows correlations between farm size and biodiversity measures without showing causal effects or controlling for crucial unobserved confounders. Therefore, it remains open if there are direct effects of farm size on biodiversity.

Nutrient flows, aerosol loading, and health

Nutrient flows are connected with FaSC through fertilizer-using farm specializations and management intensity. In the context of such specializations, farm size is of relevance for nutrient flows as change in farm size potentially changes fertilizer use efficiencies through economies of scale. Aerosol loading from FaSC might be related to specific farm specializations with high nitrogen use or livestock husbandry. The more nitrogen is used or livestock heads are involved, the higher the emissions of ammonia as an important contribution of aerosol loading.

The literature confirms the importance of those mechanisms. However, the connections between farm size, fertilizer use, and nutrient flows are multifaceted, resulting in different outcomes depending on various factors, such as efficiency, production, environmental impact, and nutrient management practices. Some studies show that larger farms are associated with less nitrogen and phosphorus flows (Liu et al. 2020; Ren et al. 2022; Zhu et al. 2022) due to higher efficiency levels of fertilizer use. Some others show that smaller farms are rather beneficial. One study estimated negative effects of farm size on fertilizer efficiency use (Hu et al. 2019), while another estimated similar effects but cautioned accelerated soil erosion and associated nutrient losses with increasing farm size (Li et al. 2020). Kenyan

study on aerosol loading shows that smaller farm sizes and higher livestock densities are related to higher particulate emissions per unit area (Ortiz-Gonzalo et al., 2017).

Agricultural production can impact health through the use of pesticides, insecticides or other chemical inputs on farms, mainly when farmers or local farm residents come into contact with chemicals or emissions. Aerosol loading, like particular matter, comes mainly from ammonia emissions in agriculture through mineral fertilizer use and livestock production (Bauer et al. 2016). These emissions are a major health problem. Exposure to these substantial risks varies across different production specializations. To consider these aspects in ex-ante models it is therefore crucial to have information about the usage of pesticides or mineral fertilizer in different production activities.

Even though there is plenty of evidence of health issues and agricultural production, we did not find literature that analyzed this relationship specifically for farm size or specializations. We find only minimal evidence that farms specialized in fruits and permanent crops exhibit the highest levels of insecticide use per hectare (Moisan et al. 2011).

Climate Change and Chemical Pollution (Novel Entities)

The impact of FaSC on climate change is intricate. Two aspects seem to be most relevant. First, farm specializations differ with respect to greenhouse gas emissions (e.g., livestock vs. crop production). Secondly, an increase in farm size might allow to realize economies of scale which can increase efficiency and decrease emissions on a per unit output bases.

Findings in the literature show that the impact of farm sizes on climate change must be analyzed within specializations. Rice producing farms for instance show patterns advantageous to larger farms due to potential efficiency gains (Kashyap & Agarwal 2021) while smaller farms in integrated crop-livestock systems show higher emissions per USD unit of production through higher livestock densities (Ortiz-Gonzalo et al. 2017). Differently, moderate-size farms specialized in beef production show lower GHG emissions, higher animal productivity, and reduced input usage than larger farms on a per output bases (Veysset et al. 2014). Regardless of farm size, specialized animal breeding farms and combinations of cattle activities contribute significantly to N₂O releases (Boeckx et al. 2001). Higher emissions are also associated with farms engaged in crop production or combined crop production and cattle breeding, while specialized animal breeding activities result in lower emissions (Samson et al. 2012). These cases highlight the possible emissions implications of farms with mixed specializations. A Norwegian case study suggests that regional concentration of agriculture might lead to a decline in emissions, whereas policies favoring small-scale farm structures could potentially increase emissions (Mittenzwei 2020). In essence, smaller farms are suggested to have higher negative impacts on climate per unit of output than larger farms. Even though animal production activities are prone to high emissions, crop production farms or mixed farms produce substantial emissions as well.

Evidence from China regarding chemical pollution shows that larger farms lower pesticide application intensity through use of agricultural machinery and different management capabilities (Gao et al. 2021). The study corroborates similar patterns found for climate change that larger farms are often more efficient in input use, and this can reduce chemical pollution.

Land Use and Water Use

Farm size and farm specialization can impact land use. Similar with the previous two themes, the most crucial mechanism is potential economies of scale or scope. However, only few evidence can be connected to land use and water use. Larger farms might be better capable of adopting crop rotations (Karlsson et al. 2022). In terms of bovine heads that are extensively managed, larger farms are also found to be less likely to abandon land (Díaz et al. 2011). In Finland, larger farms show differences in crop cover patterns with marked reduction in shares of cereal monocultures and increase in diverse crop rotations (Pirjo Peltonen-Sainio et al. 2017). FaSC might also play a role in freshwater use as some specializations require more water than others. For example, animal production is typically

found to have a larger water footprint than production of crops of similar nutritional value (Mekonnen & Hoekstra 2012).

Nutritional Security

Nutrition security depends on the ability of the farm sector to provide enough food which is related to farm size and specialization and their production efficiency.

There are several studies that study the relationship of farm size and productivity. An important information regarding this relationship is that it depends on the state of economic development in an area (Rada & Fuglie 2019). In the United States, Key (2019) finds a positive relationship between farm size and productivity whereas several studies show differing relationships. From the developing countries, a study finds an inverse relationship of farm size and productivity (Khataza et al. 2019), others find this only for smaller farm sizes (Muyanga & Jayne 2019; Yamauchi 2016). An additional study for Brazilian farms finds a u-shaped relationship of farm size and total factor productivity, which was even more pronounced for more recent data (Helfand & Taylor 2021). Other studies mainly conclude increasing productive efficiency for larger farms (Ajayi & Olutumise 2018; Ardakani et al. 2020; LaFevor & Magliocca 2020), but this hinges critically on the context of chemical fertilizer and irrigation management (LaFevor & Magliocca 2020). Further, a meta regression of 75 studies in developing countries reveals, that small-scale farms (at the lower end of the country's distribution of agricultural land size) are more productive and play a critical role in achieving food security (Azadi et al. 2023). These outcomes suggest in line with Sumner (2014) that the relationship between farm size and productivity is complex and varies across different contexts. It should be noted, that if the smaller farms are only a small fraction among all farms, their productivity advantage might be not of large relevance in providing food at the macro scale.

Farm Resilience

A resilient farm can adapt to changing conditions, absorb disturbances, and continue to provide essential goods and services, such as food and livelihoods, even in the face of adversity. Therefore, different farm specialization or farm sizes might be differently resilient. As far as resilience also stems from higher financial endowments, larger farms earning more income might be more resilient than smaller farms. Across specializations, some farms production patterns might be more flexible to adapt to disturbances, most likely being it rather mixed farms than farms that are specialized in rather a few productive orientations and with high investments in immobile assets.

Many studies show a positive relationship between farm size and income or profitability. Farm size can have a positive relationship with labor productivity and in turn influence income (Fan & Chan-Kang 2005), alongside factors such as higher education, training, experience and agricultural practices (Dolenc 2011; Donkor et al. 2022; Morantes et al. 2022; Seghezzo et al. 2020; Wang et al. 2017). Further evidence shows that expansion of farm size contributes to improved incomes for both workers and owners whereby, on-farm wage labor is positively influenced by farm size and diversification levels, while off-farm activities are more likely for farm managers with specific demographic and educational profiles (Lips et al. 2013). Relevant for the EU agricultural system, evidence shows that more CAP-subsidy-dependent farms (e.g., specialist cattle, specialist COP and small farms) face higher income risks from policy changes (Ciaian et al. 2020). Studies also highlight variations in viability across farm specializations (Bojnec & Fertó 2023; Díaz de Otálora et al. 2022; Hlavsa et al. 2020; Lawes & Kingwell 2012).

Social Equity

FaSC might be interconnected to social equity as different farm specializations or farm sizes determine income opportunities and income distribution for farmers and farm labor. Social equity within the agricultural sector might also depend on farmers' organizational power, their political representation, or their economic influence. However, important aspects of social equity in the agricultural sector are

mainly income opportunities and income distribution. The same processes of how income [farm resilience] is related to FaSC appear to be relevant for social equity. As larger farms are generally capable of generation higher incomes than smaller farms. Studies show that small farms, due to land constraints or the age of farmers, increase the risk of farmers falling into and staying within lower income groups (Headey et al. 2014; Phimister et al. 2004). Additional findings underscore the limitation of small farm sizes in driving agricultural intensification to elevate households from the bottom quartiles of the International Poverty Line (Urfels et al. 2023). However, there are studies that show the importance of smaller farms in distributing income in rural or regional contexts. Smaller farms are said to exhibit a greater proportion of diversification and contribute notably to regional economies (Kirner & Kratochvil 2006). Also, farmlands concentrated among smaller farms are positively associated with rural household incomes (Chamberlin & Jayne 2020).

As another relevant aspect of social equity, gender equality can be related to FaSC through the perspective of gender quality in management of farms (especially large or corporate farms²). Here, one may try to understand equality parameters such as gender roles, gender balance in different management levels as well as workload and time poverty of women on the farm. Evidence from Kansas shows that decrease in the average farm size has contributed to increase in the number and percentage of women farmers particularly as “principal farm operators” within the agricultural sector, paving way for more inclusive participation and allowing women to engage effectively in agricultural activities (Ball 2014).

3.1.2. Field Structural change

Agricultural landscapes considerably shape the outcomes of the SJOS. This is due among others to the high proportion of agricultural land among earth’s land use types (Foley et al., 2005), the association of agricultural production to integral ecosystem functions as well as the continuous changes in the composition and configuration of agricultural landscapes. In this section, we investigate the relationship between the SJOS thematic areas and structural changes in the agricultural landscapes. Specifically, we look at changes in the structure of the agricultural fields. For this, we define field structural change (FiSC) as the simultaneous change in the size, number and shape of agricultural fields within defined landscape boundaries. Related concepts which are described in the literature (see literature search queries in 8.1 and 8.4) are land fragmentation which entails decrease in field size and increase in number of fields (see e.g., Hartvigsen 2014; Tan et al. 2006; van Dijk 2003) and land consolidation which entails a decrease in the number of fields and increase in field size (see e.g., Xu et al., 2022; Zang et al., 2021). Both processes as well as other examples of shifts in number and size of fields tend to occur along with change in field shape.

Biodiversity

FiSC can influence genetic and functional species diversity through changes in occurrence, richness and functionality of different species on agricultural fields and landscapes. Changes in field size, shape and number can have direct impacts on species inhabiting fields and on the broader landscape species interaction. Changes in field shape determine the structure of field edges and affect the connectivity of fields to other landscape elements. Thus, it can impact migration and dispersal activities of species.

Research suggests that changes in structure of agricultural landscapes is crucial for changes in biodiversity (Bianchi et al. 2006; Gayer et al. 2019; Ruuska & Helenius 1996; Török et al. 2021). Among the evidence on structure of agricultural landscapes, we find field size to be the most represented aspect of FiSC that directly impacts biodiversity, and we find that this impact is associated with agricultural intensification (Gayer et al. 2019; Török et al. 2021). Several studies show that increasing

² The legal status of farms is not part of the terminology of farm structure in this study.

field size leads to decrease in species diversity and richness (Fried et al. 2018; Gonzalez-Estebanez et al. 2011; Stefanova & Salek 2014) while decreasing field size is beneficial for improving species richness and multitrophic diversity (Collins & Fahrig 2017; Geppert et al. 2020; Sirami et al. 2019). This is especially the case when small fields imply the presence of large semi-natural habitats between the fields (Salek et al. 2018). However, some case studies show that certain species are not impacted by FiSC in a pattern similar to the aforementioned. For example, in Germany, some Skylark species are not affected by increase in field size (Gayer et al. 2019) and larger field sizes are even found to positively correlate to the richness of web-building spiders and carnivore beetles (Galle et al. 2020).

While some studies show no evidence of the impact of change in field shape on biodiversity (Cousins & Aggemyr 2008; Dorigo et al. 2021), other studies describe patch shape as influential to species richness and density (Aksan 2023; Heegaard et al. 2007; Silveira dos Santos et al. 2022; Steel et al. 2017; Tagwireyi & Sullivan 2015; Wagner & Edwards 2001).

Nutrient Flows, Aerosol Loading, Climate Change and Chemical Pollution

These thematic areas are likely to be not impacted by FiSC directly but rather through management mechanisms that might be related to FiSC. Change in field structure is linked to management decisions and practices that impact variables such as nitrogen and phosphorus flows, particulate matter formation, GHG emissions as well as chemical production and associated pollution.

Many studies use farm size or field size as a measure of the environmental outcomes of fertilizer use based on the strong influence of fertilizer application on environmental aspects like nutrient flows (Steffen et al. 2015; Yuan et al. 2022). However, there is often no clear distinction made between farm and field size. Often referring to field size, several of these studies show an inverse association between farm size and use of chemical inputs such as fertilizer (Adamopoulos & Restuccia 2014; Foster & Rosenzweig 2022; Gao et al. 2021; Niroula & Thapa 2007; Wu et al. 2018). Gyl dengren et al. (2020) support these insights on field size and further present evidence regarding shape, showing that the accuracy and precision of nitrogen fertilizer application decreases in small and irregularly shaped fields but increases in large and regularly shaped fields. The higher use of inputs on smaller fields is linked to the economies of scale effect whereby input use efficiency increases with larger fields (Adamopoulos & Restuccia 2014). Additionally, relating to FaSC, knowledge, management skills and access to complementary technologies for improving productivity beyond chemical input use are usually higher for larger farm/ field farmers (Adamopoulos & Restuccia 2014; Foster & Rosenzweig 2022; Wu et al. 2018).

Aerosol loading and FiSC are linked by the potential different uses of machinery and fossil fuel combustion on varying agricultural field sizes and shapes. Field shape is considered a determinant of the impact of machine operations on the environment. Tractor working time, fuel consumption and aerosol emissions are found to decrease on more-square-shaped fields compared to irregularly shaped fields (Lovarelli et al. 2017). This variation is attributed to the high amount of headland turns made by tractors on irregular shapes which increases the operation time (Janulevičius & Čiplienė 2018). This is further supported by studies that show that land consolidation and the subsequent increase in field sizes are economically beneficial because they reduce field shape irregularity, travel distances, time and fuel consumption (Bahar & Kirmikil 2021; Valtiala et al. 2023).

For climate change, there is evidence that connects a negative relationship between non-renewable energy use and size of fields to GHG emissions (Mohammadi et al. 2014). Some studies also analyze the interaction between field structure and climate change on the earth system (McCord et al. 2015; McRae et al. 2012). These studies highlight the importance of field connectivity and structural change in mitigating and managing the impact of climate change on ecological processes.

For chemical pollution, we find that increasing field size is associated with increasing use of insecticide (Larsen & Noack 2021). However, the causal mechanism of how FiSC affects chemical pollution is not

clear here, so this association might simply reflect the influence of production intensity on these aspects.

Nutrition Security, Farm Resilience and Social Equity

FiSC impacts production efficiency and hence the thematic areas nutrition security, farm resilience and social equity. FiSC determines how efficiently fields can be managed and hence impacts possibilities to produce food and to ensure nutrition security, to generate farm income, and to achieve farm resilience. Mechanisms of how FiSC impacts social equity are less apparent. However, when including spatial income distribution as an aspect of social equity a potential association with FiSC might exist. Possible field structures in a location might be influenced by prevailing natural conditions (e.g., mountainous regions might not allow large regular fields). Hence, spatial heterogeneity in geography might lead to heterogeneous income possibilities depending on which field structures are possible. However, we find no evidence to test this association.

Fragmentation of land can be a threat to food production because of the possibility of land abandonment that may result from inefficient field management, reduced utility of fields and low upscaling potential (Kolecka et al. 2017; Li et al. 2018; Shi et al. 2016). This shows how nutrition security can be affected by changes in field structure. In some areas where farmers have flexible decision on land allocation, field structure may drive the allocation of land to different crops by farmers (Peltonen-Sainio et al. 2018).

Farm resilience is conditional on farm economic returns which depend on farm and field size (Arslan et al. 2020; Tanaka et al. 2023). Farmers mainly increase field size or consolidate fields as a strategy to reduce costs (Duan et al. 2021; Kirmikil & Arici 2013) because land fragmentation negatively impacts farmer's income due to smaller field parcels having lesser production efficiencies than large parcels (Niroula & Thapa 2007). When fields are consolidated, labor productivity can increase and change the labor needs (Eigner & Nuppenau 2019). Additionally, field size and shape are important structural elements that contribute to determining application and profitability of agricultural machinery (Shockley et al. 2012; Zandonadi et al. 2013). Cost of production is higher on small and irregularly shaped fields due to higher machine operation cost, higher setup costs, or higher headland yield losses (Nilsson & Rosenqvist 2021; Spekken et al. 2015).

Land Use, Water Use, Health and Economy

FiSC can lead to increase, decrease or elimination of margin elements and change in land use between fields. However, we find no evidence for this thematic area as well as health, water use and economy in our search.

3.2. Empirical work (planned) to create new empirical evidence

3.2.1. Farm Structural Change

Empirical study of farm structural change (Thünen/UBO)

Intended work: The investigation explores the relationship between farm income and farm income stability and various factors such as farm structure/type, management decisions (specifically crop rotation), and land markets (with a focus on rented land) across Europe over time. The study investigates evidence of the dynamic evolution of these drivers and examines their correlation with farm income stability, distribution, or variability. The findings will be used to complement the current set of income indicators used in ex-ante modeling for a better assessment of the Just Operating Space.

Empirical Study on Farm specialization / diversification (UBO/Thünen)

Intended work: Using FADN, we aim to study how specialization/diversification decisions impact input use efficiency. As intended in the literature review, input use efficiency is a crucial aspect impacting many aspects of SJ dimensions.

3.2.2. Field Structural change

Empirical Study on Field Structural change (UBO)

Intended work: We aim to measure field structural change empirically using detailed IACS data and potentially also remote sensing data. Further, we aim to relate the quantification to measures of farm structure (e.g., regional farm size) and other potential drivers for field structural change. Finally, we aim to improve the empirical quantification of how field structural change relates to safe outcome, primarily biodiversity.

Empirical Study on arable land use diversity (PLAB)

Intended work: Since arable land use has the most significant impact on biodiversity, it is important to know how the diversity of arable land is changing. To evaluate this, the use of remote sensing imagery is of great help, as it allows large areas to be monitored over several periods of the year. Our aim is to present a method, relying on remote sensing data, to study the temporal dynamics of crop cover, the dynamics of the green cover during non-productive periods, the temporal distribution of stubble management operations, crop die-offs due to inland water, the temporal distribution of periods of bare soil surface, or partial strip harvesting of fodder crops impacting biodiversity.

3.2.3. Farming intensity

Relations between input use and their economic viability through a flexible production function with endogenous inputs (CZU)

Intended work: We aim to provide empirical evidence on the relations between input use intensity and economic viability. We consider the proxy variable approach and address the problem with endogeneity of inputs. In particular, we focus on estimating output growth and its components attributed to quasi-fixed inputs, variable inputs, and productivity change, while treating variable inputs as endogenous. Using FADN for EU member states we study the effects of farming intensity as important process for SJOS outcomes.

Empirical Study on Typical crop rotations in Germany (UBO)

Intended work: This work aims at quantifying the diversity of crop rotations in Germany and provides insights on the introduction of beneficial crops to the present rotations. The diversity of crop rotations is linked to the SJOS dimensions biosphere integrity but also to economic dimensions. Knowledge on the present rotations is crucial for the representation of agriculture in modelling approaches. The research builds on the available spatial explicit crop data from the Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) and existing research on typologies of crop rotations and crop sequences. It is considered to extend the work to the economic evaluation of crop diversity and also include current measures of the Common Agricultural Policy on crop diversity. In course of the research, it is planned to publish one scientific paper and strongly involve regional actors of the agricultural sector.

Study of mowing / grassing intensity (Thünen/UBO)

Intended work: According to the European Grassland Butterfly Indicator report (EAA 2013), butterfly populations decreased by almost 50% between 1990 and 2011 due to changes in rural land use, specifically agricultural intensification and abandonment. These changes led to uniform grasslands,

which lack biodiversity and negatively impacted the survival of grassland butterflies that mainly thrive in traditionally farmed low-input systems.

New data sources (Lang et al. 2022), combining high-resolution economic drivers (FADN spatial) and remote sensing on crop rotation and mowing events (number of mowing events and timing of the first event) at the field level, can be used to investigate correlations between butterfly populations at the local scale over a large area (country) over time. By establishing correlations between farming systems, farm and field size, input levels (economic size units per hectare), yields and stocking density (milk yields), and farming praxis (organic and non-organic) and butterfly monitoring data, ex-ante land use scenarios (biomass demand, ruminant decline, etc.) might also be assessed on the development on the potential evolution of the grassland butterfly indicator and hence biodiversity.

3.3. Interfaces of ex-ante models

Based on the results of the literature review, we summarize and prioritize the main relations of Farm Structural Change and Field Structural Change with the SJOS dimensions. This summary is intended to inform and provide a useful basis to guide future policy modelling activities and identify the need for further empirical research.

Farm Structural Change (FaSC)

FaSC influences biodiversity mainly through changes to landscape (we discuss this in detail under FiSC below). Larger farms allow to realize economies of scale which impacts land use productivity and input use efficiency. These farm size impacts are crucial for safe outcomes such as nutrient flows, chemical pollution, climate change, and aerosol loading and just dimensions such as farm resilience and nutrient security (figure 2a). To capture this, models need to be capable of reflecting how farm sizes relate to land use productivity and input use efficiency, while empirical studies need to provide empirical information to parametrize those aspects. It might also make models which highly aggregate farming sector unsuitable and thus, might require farm-level modelling approaches which come with other challenges such as substantial input data requirements or limited regional convergence. Farm specialization, or diversification, impacts SJOS outcome as it determines possibilities for economies of scope and because specializations differ with respect to their impact on SJOS outcomes. Therefore, similarly as with farm size, models need to be able to reflect economies of scope and how different farm specializations impact SJOS outcomes, particularly with respect to safe dimensions and farm resilience. However, how farm specializations relate to the SJOS outcomes is very heterogeneous within and between thematic areas as well as across countries or regions.

The way in which FaSC aspects can be represented in simulation models is also very heterogeneous and depends on the scope and structure of the respective model. Farm models are, in general, able to capture economies of scale and scope as well as farm decisions such as exiting, enlarging or different farm specializations. However, important drivers for such decisions are exogenous to farm models and their representation requires large-scale models with commodity and labor markets. The requirement of farm-level modelling approaches for FaSC aspects, and larger-scale models that capture drivers of FaSC infers the need for model coupling to fully capture FaSC.

Only a small number of the reviewed studies particularly quantified the relationship between FaSC and thematic areas of the SJOS in European countries. Therefore, there is need for further research on this relationship, especially across the just thematic areas. Additionally, empirical studies need to provide the bases to parameterize identified effects and it will be valuable for future studies to show more causal mechanisms rather than correlational evidence for thematic areas of land use and water use and, to reveal the distinctive differences in farm resilience between different farm specializations.

Field Structural Change (FiSC)

Two main mechanisms are relevant for FiSC. First, FiSC directly impacts biodiversity by affecting migration and dispersal possibilities of species on the landscape and by affecting the configuration of

semi-natural habitats within landscapes. Secondly, FiSC can vary the efficiency of management, hence land productivity and input use efficiency. This indirectly impacts safe dimensions such as nutrient flows, aerosol loading, climate change as well as chemical pollution (figure 2b), and also just dimensions such as nutrition security and farm resilience. However, we find no literature evidence of FiSC impacting thematic areas of land use, water use, social equity, health and economy.

Modelling of FiSC relation to biodiversity requires that models are capable to capture how different field sizes, shapes and their changes are impacted by policies and economic drivers. Additionally, they need to capture how FiSC relates to biodiversity outcomes. This requires a clear definition of appropriate measures for FiSC, and parameterizing their relation to biodiversity outcomes. Models also need to reflect how FiSC translates into land productivity, yield and production costs. Similar to the OFTU and FaSC this allows to assess the indirect impacts of FiSC on SJOS outcomes.

The large volume of evidence relating to biodiversity mostly provides direction of association. Some further provide statistical estimates of the predictive power of the various applied empirical models used to analyze the association. However, there is a scarcity of studies that provide actual causal estimates. Also, heterogeneity of evidence between species and geography makes it difficult to generalize findings for modelling. Many studies regarding nutrient flows come from study areas in Asia which might not easily be transferred to EU agriculture. Nutrition security and farm resilience have studies which qualitatively relate to FiSC, but the strength of the effect and the causal mechanisms are not clearly identified. There is little evidence for expected relation to climate change and chemical pollution. Thus, there is need for further empirical research that delves into the causal relationships with FiSC. The empirical research needs to identify appropriate measures to quantify the relevant aspects of FiSC and how they relate to biodiversity outcomes and the efficiency of management that impacts other outcomes.

Figure 2 Categorization of SJOS thematic areas according to the literature review findings on (A) Farm Structural Change (FaSC) and (B) Field Structural Change (FiSC).

4. TASK 3.3 DEMAND SIDE: CONSUMER DIETS / PREFERENCES / WASTE (WP LEAD: UCSC)

In this section, we consider aspects related to changes in consumer preferences (meats, vegetable proteins and sugar-sweetened beverages) and how they relate to SJOS outcomes. Specifically, we consider how diets related to Human Health, climate change, biodiversity, and the local food systems. Additionally, we consider the relationship between food waste and food security and the economy.

We first present the results to the literature review and then discuss the planned empirical activities within the task, as well as connection to ex-ante models.

4.1. Literature Review of existing empirical evidence

The global food system poses significant challenges to both environmental sustainability and social justice. It is a major contributor to climate change, resource depletion, and persistent inequalities in income, education, and societal well-being. Understanding the complex dynamics of food systems necessitates examining both supply-side and demand-side drivers. This review centers on the demand side, exploring how consumer choices and behaviors relate to the goals of the Safe and Just Operating Space (SJOS), focusing on two critical demand-side aspects of agri-food system transitions toward the SJOS: “dietary choices” and “food waste” patterns. In detail, we investigate the existing evidence on the impact of dietary choices and food wastes on climate change (and broader sustainability), biodiversity, health, food & nutrition security and economics as these emerge as the primary SJOS indicators to be affected by dietary choices and food waste.

Diet and Human Health

The effect of diet on human health is well established in food science. There are many longitudinal studies that monitor the diet of people and their health status over a long period of time. Global Burden of Diseases of Lancet Institute publishes meta-analysis of such studies. The outcome of these studies shows that there is a stable relationship between diet and health outcomes. Even though elaboration on the exact relationship between diet and the health outcomes is out of scope of this review, in the following we will point out the most important findings and trends in the literature.

The reviewed literature overwhelmingly demonstrates a global dietary shift away from minimally processed, whole foods toward highly processed, convenience-oriented food products. This trend, influenced by urbanization, income changes, and evolving employment patterns, is strongly associated with decreased consumption of nutrient-rich foods and increased reliance on animal-source products. In adolescence, this dietary shift is intertwined with complex social, cognitive, and emotional changes (Sinai et al 2021). Research indicates that dietary patterns established at this critical stage have significant long-term health consequences, including increased risk of obesity and chronic diseases (Sinai et al. 2021; Yusuf et al 2020).

Across various global contexts, urbanization, rising incomes, and women's increased participation in the workforce have driven changes in food preferences and consumption. This has led to increased demand for highly processed foods that are often high in sugar, salt, and saturated fats (Ambikapathi et al 2022). While this dietary shift has contributed to a decrease in micronutrient deficiencies among some populations, the long-term consequences for health are substantial. Studies repeatedly show a strong association with increased risk of cardiometabolic diseases (Ambikapathi et al 2022). It is crucial to note that dietary transitions occur unevenly among and within populations. Factors like income, food security, and local food environments strongly influence dietary choices (Ambikapathi et al 2022; Poole et al 2021).

The literature presents strong evidence that substituting whole, plant-based foods for highly processed foods and some animal products yields significant health benefits. Plant-forward dietary patterns rich in fruits, vegetables, whole grains, and legumes are associated with decreased mortality and reduced incidence of cardiovascular disease, some cancers, and other chronic diseases (Gastaldello et al 2022; Kim, Caulfield et al 2018; Li et al 2021). However, not all plant-based diets produce equal health outcomes. Diets centred around processed plant-based foods with high sugar, refined grain, and unhealthy fat content can increase the risk of chronic diseases (Gastaldello et al., 2022). Research suggests that even modest dietary adjustments can have substantial health impacts. Targeted substitutions of specific food categories offer a feasible strategy to improve health without necessitating extreme dietary overhauls (Stylianou et al 2021).

While the benefits of plant-forward diets are well-supported, questions remain about the ideal intake of animal-source foods and the long-term health effects of certain plant-based alternatives (Geibel et al 2021; Gastaldello et al 2022). The relationship between diet and health is complex. Individual characteristics, food accessibility and affordability, as well as broader environmental factors significantly influence both dietary choices and health outcomes (Finaret et al 2019).

Diet and climate change

The agricultural sector is the second-highest greenhouse gas (GHG) emitter after the energy sector as it contributes to about 30% of total GHGs (Wirsenius et al., 2011; Caillavet et al., 2016, 2019; FAO, 2017). Among agricultural activities, livestock production – especially ruminant meat and dairy production - is the most polluting sector as it contributes for more than one third of total GHGs from the agri-food supply-chain (Bonnet et al., 2018, 2020; Caillavet et al., 2019; Tiboldo et al., 2022). As world meat demand has been steadily increasing over time because of population and income growth as well as the increasing preference for animal proteins, the impact of the agri-food sector on climate change is expected to dramatically increase in the future (Wellesley et al., 2015; Bonnet et al., 2018; Caillavet et al., 2019). According to some studies, in 2050 ruminant meat alone will be responsible for about two-thirds of global GHGs from agriculture (Hedenus et al., 2014; Bonnet et al., 2020). As animal-based foods are relatively more carbon and resource intensive (per mass unit) to produce than plant-based foods (for instance in terms of water and land use) (Clark & Tilman, 2017; Clune et al., 2017; Fresán et al., 2019; Bonnet et al., 2020), the agricultural economics research has recently devoted an increasing attention on the potential environmental impacts of changes in current dietary patterns especially towards more plant-based diets.

However, to promote sustainable food systems through policy instruments, it is crucial to consider not only the nutritional values and emissions of individual products, but also the nutritional contribution to the overall diet and its total emissions (Röös et al., 2015; Burgaz et al., 2023). This requires a holistic approach. The literature indicates that environmental and nutritional goals are closely related, and a diet with a lower impact on the climate is usually the most nutritionally beneficial option (e.g., Hallström et al., 2014; van Dooren et al., 2014; Xia et al., 2023). Previous research has primarily evaluated the impact of diets based on GHGs, and all studies agree that substituting animal products with plant-based foods in a diet enhances its environmental performance (GHGs) while maintaining nutritional balance. Research has demonstrated that ruminant meats have the highest environmental impact among animal products. Reducing ruminant meat consumption, if not switching entirely to a plant-based diet, can, therefore, significantly improve dietary sustainability.

In light of these findings, there is growing support in the literature for policies that discourage the consumption of high climate-impact foods and encourage the consumption of nutritious and lower-emitting products. To reduce the impact of agri-food chains on GHGs, several policy alternatives have been suggested, including market-based approaches (e.g., Pigouvian taxes or direct subsidies) and informational tools (Arrieta and González 2018; Bryngelsson et al. 2016; Deckers 2010; Huan-Niemi et al. 2020; van Dooren et al. 2018; Xiong et al. 2020). However, educational and informational programs

about the environmental impacts of food and drink production (e.g., carbon labels) have shown to have limited effectiveness in influencing food consumption patterns and reducing GHGs from the food system in the long run (European Commission, 2012; Edjabou and Smed 2013; Elofsson et al. 2016). This may be partly explained by the public good nature of GHGs and climate impacts (Elofsson et al. 2016).

Therefore, over the last decade, a novel stream of literature has investigated the potential impacts of carbon taxes on food consumption on GHGs from the agri-food system. Starting from the seminal work of Wirsenius et al. (2011), several studies investigate how carbon taxes proportional to the GHGs generated by each food product (also known as Pigouvian taxes) may affect food consumption patterns in a country, and so, the total GHGs from the food system. Overall, these studies show that GHGs on foods may be a cost-effective policy tool for reducing GHGs from the agri-food sector, with the level of total GHGs mitigation depending on the number of food categories affected (e.g., meat only, all animal foods, all foods), the type of tax scheme adopted (uncompensated or compensated), and the tax rate (i.e. the value of the social carbon cost as provided from official statistics). In detail, the highest GHGs abatement (up to -20%) is achieved when simulating uncompensated tax schemes affecting all food prices (e.g., Edjabou & Smed, 2013; Revoredo-Giha et al., 2018). Moreover, the GHGs mitigation potential increases with the estimated value for the social cost of carbon (e.g., Bonnet et al., 2018; Caillavet et al., 2019).

Despite their effectiveness in terms of GHGs mitigation, carbon taxes on foods may also have some unintended consequences on consumers' health, as they affect the nutritional composition of the diet (Briggs et al., 2013; Caillavet et al., 2019). Moreover, as for other food taxation, carbon taxes may be regressive. As low-income households spend a higher share of their income on food purchases and they usually buy cheaper products, they experience higher percentage changes in food prices and they are more burdened by carbon taxes than relatively more affluent consumers (García-Muros et al., 2017; Caillavet et al., 2019; Tiboldo et al., 2022). For this reason, the research in this field has evolved over time to also account for the potential impacts of carbon taxes on foods on population-wide nutritional outcomes (e.g. Edjabou & Smed, 2013), and also, for the distributional implications of this fiscal policies, both from a fiscal and a nutritional perspective, with a special focus on most vulnerable socio-economic groups (i.e., low-income households and household with children) (e.g., Kehlbacher et al., 2016; Caillavet et al., 2019; García-Muros et al., 2017; Tiboldo et al., 2022).

Overall, the results from these studies show that the convergence between environmental, nutritional and social equity goals is difficult to achieve and it strongly depends on the carbon tax design (Bonnet et al., 2020).

Diet and biodiversity

The relationship between food systems and biodiversity is a critical area of study within environmental science and sustainability research. The global food system is widely recognized as a major driver of biodiversity loss, with food production playing a significant role in shaping land use, habitat conversion, and ecosystem degradation (Campbell et al., 2017; IPCC, 2019). While there is extensive literature documenting the environmental consequences of food production systems, studies exploring the effects of consumer behaviour on biodiversity loss and researching the potential of dietary shifts to reduce biodiversity loss are relatively recent phenomena in the scientific literature.

Higher incomes and the so-called 'westernization of diets' often result in higher consumption of animal-based foods that have much larger negative environmental effects, including biodiversity impacts, as compared to plant-based foods (Díaz et al., 2019). As a result of these processes, combined with the projected global population and income growth, food demand is also likely to continue growing, especially for animal-based foods (FAO, 2018; OECD/FAO, 2021) This will lead to further biodiversity loss unless there is a profound change in the food systems (Leclère et al., 2020; Visconti

et al., 2016). Consequently, the potential of dietary shifts to mitigate biodiversity loss has gained attention in recent years.

Exploring the dietary impacts on biodiversity results in identifying several key concepts and themes. First, diet influences biodiversity through two main channels: agricultural expansion and intensification of agricultural practices (Benton et al., 2021, Díaz et al., 2019). Agricultural expansion involves the conversion of natural habitats, such as forests and grasslands, into agricultural land to meet the growing demand for food, resulting in habitat loss, fragmentation, and degradation, leading to declines in biodiversity (Foley et al., 2005). Intensification of agricultural practices refers to the increased use of inputs such as fertilizers, pesticides, and irrigation to boost crop yields. This may reduce agricultural expansion, on the one hand, but might also lead to negative environmental consequences, including biodiversity loss (Sánchez-Bayo & Wyckhuys, 2019, Tilman et al., 2011). Food demand is linked to both processes in multiple ways, such as through quantity, variety (e.g. meat vs. legumes) and quality of food (organic vs. conventional agriculture sourced) consumed.

The adoption of healthier and more sustainable dietary patterns, mainly consisting of plant-based diets, has been proposed as a strategy to reduce the environmental footprint of food production systems (Davis et al., 2023). Another important component of biodiversity-friendly food consumption is avoiding overconsumption, which means significant reduction of energy intake in many high-income countries (Ganivet, 2020, Willet et al. 2019). Novel foods could be a viable pathway to reducing the biodiversity impacts of food systems. For example, partial replacement of animal source foods with plant-based meat and milk alternatives could significantly reduce land use impacts associated with livestock production (Kozicka et al., 2023). Moreover, studies have highlighted the importance of considering trade-mediated inter-regional impacts of diets on biodiversity loss (Hentschl et al., 2023, Kozicka et al. 2023). Another important area of research considers interactions between land and sea use in food systems and trade-offs that might arise (Cottrell et al., 2018). For example, increasing consumption of seaweed could reduce land-based agricultural pressures and mitigate biodiversity loss (Spillias et al., 2023). However, careful assessment of the potential impacts of seaweed farming on marine ecosystems is essential to ensure sustainability.

Diet and economics: Local food systems

Local food, or locally produced food, does not have a unified and highly consensual definition (Brune et al. 2023). It can refer to food that is produced in the same county, region, or state where it is consumed or the food that is produced within a certain distance from the marketing outlet. It can also refer to the food that is directly purchased from farmers. In most studies, local food is considered to be the food that is produced and consumed within a certain geographical area, like a village, county, city or state. Local food is part of the local food system (LFS) which comprises production, distribution, and consumption of local foods.

Local food systems, which rely on small farms, are considered to be more reliable and resilient compared to the global food system (Stephens et al. 2020). The European Commission, in the "Farm to Fork Strategy" of 2020, praises short food supply chains which rely less on long-haul transportation infrastructure. Local food systems are also considered to be a more equitable food system compared to other food systems (Allen 2010).

Local food systems are believed to have socioeconomic, environmental and health benefits. From an economic point of view, consuming local foods generates a demand for local producers and, therefore, contributes to local employment. An increase in local employment, in turn, increases the income of the residents. The positive effect on employment has spillovers in the social safety and well-being of counties. Local food systems are also more resilient than non-local food systems as they depend less on transportation and are less affected by national and international supply disruptions. Local food systems are considered to be environmentally friendly food systems as the food travels less, consumes less energy for preservation and storage and requires less use of pesticides and fertilizer. Consuming

local food can be a healthy choice as local foods are usually fresher and less processed than imported foods, provided that local producers adhere to the quality standards in the production process.

Local food, however, is not necessarily the most cost-effective choice for some consumers, especially low-income families. The reason is that large food producers with global reach often outcompete local and small food producers in terms of price and availability. As a result, local food is usually more expensive than imported food. Therefore, consumers have to pay a price premium for local food. In addition, local fresh food is not necessarily superior to processed food in terms of nutritional value (Miller and Knudsen 2014; Rickman et al. 2007). In addition, local food is not usually subject to the same type of stringent standards and regulations that imported foods are subjected to. Next, local food systems, while being more resilient, might not be able to produce enough food for the local population due to resource constraints. Kinnunen et al. (2020) estimate that only about 11-28 per cent of the global population may acquire their demand for specific crops from a 100-kilometre radius. Finally, relying on local food systems might result in over extraction of natural resources such as water and land. Overall, local food systems seem to be a promising venue that positively contributes to the local communities but cannot, and probably should not, be regarded as a substitute to non-local food systems.

Food waste and food security

Food loss and waste (FLW) occur along the entire food supply chain, on its way from field to consumption, and this poses a challenge to both food security and sustainability in the agri-food systems. FLW has become a relevant factor that contributed to increase food security worldwide (Geislar, 2019). It is generally assumed that reducing food loss and waste means more food is available for human consumption and this may be translated into benefits in nutrition and food security (i.e., Philippidis et al. 2019, Santeramo, 2021). However, the actual effects can be complex. The impacts of reducing food loss and waste on food security and nutrition depend on the geographical locations of populations facing food insecurity or nutritional vulnerability. Additionally, it may be influenced by the specific stages within the food supply chain that are targeted for reduction efforts.

The concept of food security, according to FAO, is defined as when “all people at all times, have physical and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food to meet their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life”. Since the early 2010s, the number of articles discussing FLW has notably increased once this topic entered the policy and research agenda (FAO, 2011, FAO, 2019, UNEP, 2021; Kummur et al. 2012; Xue et al. 2017; Schanes et al. 2018). In this overview of literature, we highlight several studies on the relationship between food waste and food security.

Some studies, focusing on the entire food supply chain, attempt to understand the origins of food security, and thus, of the underlying factors of food waste so that information can be used to implement interventions to improve the levels of food security (i.e., Irani and Sharif, 2016). Studies also investigate the effects of reducing food loss and waste in developing countries, examining both food security and environmental impacts in international food markets using simulation models (i.e., Munesue et al. 2015). However, given that the quantity of food wasted at the household level is much greater than that of other food supply chain levels (Hebrok and Heidenstrøm, 2019), the literature associated with food security in the context of downstream food waste is narrower.

At the consumer level, several insightful studies investigate the intersection of food waste, food insecurity, and related behaviours with different methods to provide the necessary evidence to support policymakers in developing targeted strategies to reduce food waste, improve access to food for vulnerable populations and promote more sustainable consumption patterns. Thus, based on a pilot study, Armstrong et al. (2021) delved into the connection between food waste, food insecurity, and consumer behaviours in the UK post-COVID lockdown. Fami et al. (2021) examined the link between food waste and food security in Tehran, highlighting the potential for reducing food waste to alleviate food insecurity in urban Iranian households. Althumiri et al. (2021) explored the relationship

between food waste and food insecurity at household and individual levels in Saudi Arabia, finding a positive association between the two. Additionally, Garcia-Silva et al. (2017) evaluated a public-private partnership in Orange County (USA) aimed at reducing food insecurity and waste through community education on food donations. Jereme et al. (2017) investigated the potential of utilizing edible food waste from households, restaurants, and hotels to alleviate food insecurity in Malaysia, suggesting that donating these surplus foods to food banks could be an effective strategy. Min et al. (2021) provided evidence for the idea that enhancing the dietary knowledge of food decision-makers could have a substantial impact on reducing food waste.

Food waste and climate and sustainability

Given the far-reaching implications for both environmental and social well-being, as the world's population expands and consumption habits change, the inefficiencies which are embedded in the food system are becoming increasingly evident. The substantial quantity of food discarded along the chain every year, particularly at consumption level, does not only imply a wasteful use of limited resources like land, water and energy but also has a role to play in the generation of GHG emissions. Thus, addressing food waste not only promotes environmental sustainability and combats climate change but also contributes to the development of a fairer and more resilient food system for both present and future generations.

Over the past decade, there has been a growing number of studies addressing the impacts of food loss and waste (FLW) on sustainability and climate change. These studies have focused on several main themes. Firstly, there is the quantification of the impacts of food waste management through life cycle assessments (e.g., Kim and Kim, 2010; Bernstad and la Cour Jansen, 2011; Edwards et al., 2018; Slorach et al., 2019 for households; Eriksson et al., 2015; Vandermeersch et al., 2014 for retailers; Tong et al., 2018 for out-of-home settings). Secondly, research has delved into measuring the climate impact of household consumption (i.e., Silvennoinen et al., 2022) and out-of-home settings, including the food service sector and canteens (Oliveira et al., 2016; Garcia-Herrero et al., 2021; Shankar et al., 2022; Nandhivarman et al., 2015). Studies have also focused on collecting new data on food waste management at the local level (Derqui and Grimaldi, 2020).

Another theme revolves around consumers' behaviour (i.e., van Giesen and de Hooge 2019; Gracia and Gómez 2020; Aschemann-Witzel et al 2018; Attiq et al 2021; Roe et al 2022, Nwankwo-Ojionu et al 2023, Reisch et al 2021), others examined the impact of food waste management (i.e., Martin-Rios et al 2021; Zan et al 2022; Tonini et al 2020; Iacovidou and Voulvoulis, 2019; Huang et al 2020; Xiao and Siu 2018), while there are other works exploring other food waste uses like composting (i.e., Waitt and Rankin 2022, Melikoglu and Cinel 2020) and food waste recycling experiences (Xiao and Siu, 2018). Also, studies addressed the assessment of the food-waste-water-energy nexus (i.e., Slorach et al., 2020, Zan et al., 2022, Melikoglu and Cinel, 2020) and the effect on water resources (Chapagain and James, 2013).

Other topics include the relationship with diet quality and nutritional quality as unexpected relations with food waste may arise (Conrad et al., 2018, Conrad and Blackstone, 2021; Aldaco et al., 2020), the sustainability of the food system either by analyzing the impact of FLW on production and consumption through the lens of interrelated implications (i.e., Vittuari et al. 2019), by assessing the existence of trade-offs derived from food waste interventions (Latka et al. 2022) or through the assessment of valorization options into energy (i.e., Dou et al., 2018, Albizzati et al., 2021, Han et al., 2022, Feiz et al., 2022, Zhang et al., 2020). Studies have also addressed the sustainability of food waste prevention measures (i.e., Goossens et al. 2019; Mourad 2016). Lastly, fewer studies review the narrative on food waste and environmental sustainability with diverse motivations and regions object of analysis (i.e., Baig et al., 2019 for Saudi Arabia, Conrad and Blackstone, 2021 for the USA).

Food waste and economy

The burgeoning literature connecting consumer food waste (as most food wasted along the chain in developed regions occurs at consumption stage) and the economic dimension offers multiple approaches. These are ranging from the analysis of economic costs and benefits of food waste reduction with model-based studies to the identification of drivers employing different instruments like partial equilibrium models (i.e., Rutten, 2013, Höjgård et al 2013), computable general equilibrium models (i.e., Campoy-Muñoz et al 2017, Philippidis et al 2019, Barrera and Hertel, 2021) or econometric modeling (i.e., Ellison and Lusk, 2016).

Studies also address the assessment of intricate aspects of consumers' behaviour, for instance, identifying drivers (i.e., Aschemann-Witzel et al 2015, Dou et al 2016; Thyberg and Tonjes 2016, Ellison and Lusk, 2016, Lusk and Ellison 2017) and attitudes (i.e., Graham-Rowe et al 2015, Qi and Roe 2016, Coderoni and Perito, 2020), as well as diverging from aforementioned simulation models considering food waste reduction and prevention (i.e., Quested et al 2013, Reynolds et al 2019, Richards and Hamilton, 2018), unraveling drivers or antecedents of food waste (i.e., Schanes et al 2018, Porpino et al 2015).

The limited number of studies focused on the development of foundational economic model (i.e., Drabik et al 2019, de Gorter et al 2021) contrasts with the numerous empirical studies dealing with techno-economic evaluation of ways of energy production from food waste (i.e., Han et al 2016, Rajendran and Han, 2021), with regulations and initiatives (i.e., DeLorenzo et al 2019, Ryen and Babbitt 2022) and, recently gaining followers, the adoption of a circular economic model framework with different topics such as household food waste management (i.e., Tonini et al 2020,), or exploring the ways in which consumers can participate in closing loops concerning food waste (i.e., Borrello et al 2017, de Souza et al 2021, Teigiserova et al 2020, Slorach et al 2019b). Given the differences among existing studies, systematic reviews have also been conducted to enhance the understanding about food waste and this circular economy framework (Aschemann-Witzel and Stangherlin 2021, de Oliveira et al 2021, Tamasiga et al 2022, Alonso-Muñoz et al 2022).

4.2. Empirical work (planned) to create new empirical evidence

4.2.1. Heterogeneity in demand systems of EU27 households (WU/WR)

Intended work: Many ex-ante models make use of one or a few elasticities for all households represented in the model. This assumes that there are no differences in elasticities between different households within and between EU27 countries. The aim of this research is to determine how big the heterogeneity in elasticities is between different household types.

For this household budget survey (HBS) data and price data of individual member states will be used. The households in the HBS will be divided into clusters using machine learning techniques. For each cluster price- and income elasticities will be estimated. Meta-analysis techniques will be used to analyse the heterogeneity in elasticities between the different clusters.

4.2.2. Evolution of French legume consumption and determinant of consumers' adoption (INRAE)

Intended work: Legumes contribute to meet sustainability challenges in a context of transition towards more sustainable agriculture and diets. They have the advantage of containing protein, making them an alternative food source to meat for protein intake. However, consumption of legumes remains low in Europe. In this work, we will thus investigate how the consumption of pulses can be increased.

We will use French consumption of legumes as a case study and analyse whether it is possible to increase both the number of consumers of pulses and the quantity consumed. Using French panel data (Kantar Worldpanel) from 2002 to 2019, we will first characterise, represent and analyse the evolution patterns of total and per capita purchased quantities of legumes (in dry legume equivalent). We will then estimate a Hurdle model for each year to identify the socio-demographic determinants that may affect the probability of purchase and the quantities purchased, as well as their evolution and robustness over time.

4.2.3. Evolution of food purchases in France and its impact on nutritional quality and health on the one hand, and on the environment on the other (INRAE)

Intended work: We propose to analyse the evolution of food purchases in France and its impact on nutritional quality on the one hand, and on the environment on the other. To this end, we will make use of the French panel data on household purchases, Kantar World Panel and complement those purchases data with other datasets covering food product characteristics and recipe.

Our analysis is divided into two parts. The first part will focus on the characterization of food purchases between 2002 and 2019 and will analyse the socio-economic determinants of consumer choices. To this end, we propose to characterize food purchases according to the major product categories as identified in the nutritional guidelines: fruits and vegetables; cereals; meat, fish and eggs; dairy products; and sweet, fatty and salty foods. Our objective is to understand how overall food purchases change over time by major food category. The second component will analyse how the evolution of food purchases translates into nutritional and environmental qualities such as carbon footprint and how those qualities could vary over households.

4.2.4. Interdependencies and trade-offs between sustainability, nutritional and social equity goals: a case study on food taxes in Italy (UCSC)

Intended work: The existing evidence on carbon taxes on foods for sustainability show how the convergence between environmental, nutritional and social equity goals is difficult to achieve and it strongly depends on taxes design (Bonnet et al., 2020). Therefore, the main goal of this analysis is to further investigate the potential interdependencies, complementarities, and trade-offs among environmental, nutritional, and social equity goals in the development and implementation of specific fiscal policies affecting food prices to achieve healthier and more sustainable food consumption patterns in Italy.

To do so, we will use food purchase data for a representative sample of Italian households augmented with information on the nutritional characteristics and the environmental footprint of foods available from official statistics at the national level to estimate food demand in Italy. The demand model specification will be flexible enough to allow price sensitivities to vary across different socio-economic groups. The estimated results will then be used to derive price elasticities which will be employed to simulate potential changes in food purchase patterns after the introduction of different fiscal policies affecting food prices (e.g., environmental related or health related taxes on foods), especially focusing on the substitution between animal and vegetable proteins. We will then derive the potential impacts of these policies on population-wide nutritional outcomes, as well as on the environmental footprint of food purchases. As our empirical model specification allows price sensitivities to differ across different socio-economic groups, we will also be able to derive the distributional implications of these policies both from a nutritional and a fiscal standpoint. Therefore, this analysis will enable us to

evaluate how fiscal policies targeting healthier and more sustainable food consumption patterns may affect different dimensions of the SJOS.

As one of the main limitations of studies assessing the potential impact of food taxes are the sometimes overly restrictive supply-side assumptions (e.g., passive pricing and perfect price transmission along agri-food chains) (Bonnet and Réquillart 2013a; 2013b; Bonnet, Bouamra-Mechemache, and Corre 2018), we will also develop a case study investigating how strategic behaviour along modern agri-food chains may affect the expected outcomes of food taxation

4.2.5. EU member state household food waste rates (CITA)

Intended work: We aim to investigate the influence of key determinants on food waste within a sample of the 27 European Union Member States. To achieve this, we have compiled a dataset containing food waste rates for households at the national level, as well as for various food groups, along with pertinent determinants. We aim to conduct ex-post analysis using the most adequate econometric model specification to ascertain the drivers of food waste and food waste rates. Further, we aim to implement the econometric insights into a CGE simulation model to generate projections of future food waste rates within a status quo baseline.

4.3. Interfaces to ex-ante models

The elasticities that will be derived under task 4.2.1 will be used to develop a new microsimulation model as part of WP7. The new model will be able to assess how price- and income changes will have heterogeneous effects on food consumption of different households in the EU27.

Despite being mainly focused on the Italian case study, the empirical results from task 4.2.4 will provide a more granular overview of substitution patterns among animal and vegetable proteins, therefore potentially contributing to improving the substitution elasticities in large-scale market model (e.g., CAPRI or MAGNET) in order to better simulate the impact of demand side policy changes.

5. CONCLUSION

This preliminary deliverable presents the work already conducted within the first half of the duration of WP3, until M18. The work conducted so far mainly consists of a systematic literature review to collect existing knowledge on how non-policy processes relate to relevant SJ dimensions. This review aims to prioritize which processes are most important to consider in ex-ante models when aiming to model policy effects on SJOS outcomes. Additionally, we outline a tentative plan of the empirical activities we aim to conduct in the second half of WP3.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This document was produced under the terms and conditions of Grant Agreement No. 101060075 for the European Commission. It does not necessarily reflect the view of the European Union and in no way anticipates the Commission's future policy in this area.

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8. APPENDIX 1

8.1. Keywords and General Structure of Search Queries Used for Literature Search on Web of Science

		Literature Search Keywords and Structural Formation of Search Queries
	Basic structure	“Decision category keyword(s)” and agricultur* and dimension keyword(s) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)
Decision Categories	On-farm technology usage	Land management, machinery, biotechnology, precision farming, organic farming, smart farming Y: “land management” or machinery or biotechnolog* or ((precision or smart or organic) NEAR/1 farming)
	Farm structural change	Y: “farm struct*” or “farm speciali*” or “farm size*”

	Field structural change	Field shape, parcel shape, field size, parcel size, field structure, parcel structure Y: (“field shape” or “parcel shape”) or (“field size” or “parcel size”) or (“field structur*” or “parcel structur*”)
SOS Dimensions	Biodiversity	Biodiversity, “genetic diversity”, “functional diversity”, “biosphere integrity”, (extinction NEAR/2 rate), (species NEAR/2 variability) Y and agricultur* and (biodiversity or “genetic diversity” or “functional diversity” or “biosphere integrity” or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)
	Climate change	“climate change”, “greenhouse gas*”, “global warming” Y and agricultur* and (“climate change” or “greenhouse gas*” or “global warming”) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)
	Nutrient flows	((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)) Y and agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)
	Land use	“forest cover” or (land NEAR/2 conversion) or deforestation or “land use change” Y and agricultur*and (“forest cover” or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or “land use change”) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)
	Water use	((groundwater or freshwater or “blue water” or “surface water*”) NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use))

	<p>Y and agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or “blue water” or “surface water*”) NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p>
Chemical pollution (Novel entities)	<p>“chemical pollut*”, “novel entities”, chlorofluorocarbon, pesticide, “heavy metal”, microplastics</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and (“chemical pollut*” or “novel entities” or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal”) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p>
Aerosol loading	<p>air, air pollution, “air pollut*”, “particulate matter”, emission of sulphur, nitrate and carbon</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p>
Nutrition security	<p>food, undernourishment, hunger</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p>
Health	<p>health</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and health (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p>
Social equity	<p>Gender, education, social equity</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and (gender or (gender NEAR/2 equality) or educat* or literacy or “social equity”) (Topic) and Agriculture,</p>

	Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)
Economy	Energy, “sectoral VAD”, “sectoral employment”, “sectoral wages” Y and energy (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)
Income: additional search area used to generate income related findings that have been used under social equity and farm resilience areas within the sections	income or (income NEAR work) Y and agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)
Farm resilience	resilien* Y and resilien* (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)

8.2. On-Farm Technology Usage Search Queries and Results

	Full Search Query	Date of Last Search	Records found	Relevant Studies
Biodiversity	(TS=(“land management” or machinery or biotechnolog* or ((precision or smart or organic) NEAR/1 farming)) AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or “genetic diversity” or “functional diversity” or “biosphere integrity” or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR	2023-11-22	347	20

	Agricultural Economics & Policy)			
Climate change	(TS=(“land management” or machinery or biotechnolog* or ((precision or smart or organic) NEAR/1 farming)) AND TS=(agricultur* and (“climate change” or “greenhouse gas*” or “global warming”))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-11-22	309	36
Nutrient flows	(TS=(“land management” or machinery or biotechnolog* or ((precision or smart or organic) NEAR/1 farming)) AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-11-22	181	5
Land use	(TS=(“land management” or machinery or biotechnolog* or ((precision or smart or organic) NEAR/1 farming)) AND TS=(agricultur* and (“forest cover” or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or “land use change”))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-11-22	88	3
Water use	(TS=(“land management” or machinery or biotechnolog* or ((precision or smart or organic) NEAR/1 farming))	2023-11-22	8	0

	AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or “blue water” or “surface water*”) NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)			
Chemical pollution (Novel entities)	(TS=(“land management” or machinery or biotechnolog* or ((precision or smart or organic) NEAR/1 farming)) AND TS=(agricultur* and (“chemical pollut*” or “novel entities” or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal”))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-11-22	243	14
Aerosol loading	(TS=(“land management” or machinery or biotechnolog* or ((precision or smart or organic) NEAR/1 farming)) AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-11-22	47	0
Nutrition Security	(TS=(“land management” or machinery or biotechnolog* or ((precision or smart or organic) NEAR/1 farming)) AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or	2023-11-22	895	11

	hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)			
Health	(TS=(“land management” or machinery or biotechnolog* or ((precision or smart or organic) NEAR/1 farming)) AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-11-22	293	17
Social equity	(TS=(“land management” or machinery or biotechnolog* or ((precision or smart or organic) NEAR/1 farming)) AND TS=(agricultur* and gender or (gender NEAR/2 equality) or educat* or literacy or “social equity”)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-11-22	193	0
Economy	(TS=(“land management” or machinery or biotechnolog* or ((precision or smart or organic) NEAR/1 farming)) AND TS=(agricultur* and energy or (sector* NEAR/2 (VAD or employment or wage*)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-11-22	284	15
Income & work: findings from here	(TS=(“land management” or machinery or biotechnolog* or ((precision or smart or organic) NEAR/1 farming))	2023-11-22	220	10

are used under social equity and farm resilience	AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)			
Farm resilience	(TS=(“land management” or machinery or biotechnolog* or ((precision or smart or organic) NEAR/1 farming)) AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-11-22	83	0
Total			3191	131

8.3. Farm Structural Change Search Queries and Results

	Full Search Query	Date of Last Search	Records found	Relevant Studies
Biodiversity	TS=(“farm struct*” and agricultur* and (biodiversity or “genetic diversity” or “functional diversity” or “biosphere integrity” or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability))) OR TS=(“farm speciali*” and agricultur* and (biodiversity or “genetic diversity” or “functional diversity” or “biosphere integrity” or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability))) OR TS=(“farm size*” and agricultur* and (biodiversity or “genetic diversity” or “functional diversity” or “biosphere integrity” or	2023-07-26	48	5

	(extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)			
Climate	TS=(“farm struct*” and agricultur* and (“climate change” or “greenhouse gas*” or “global warming”)) OR TS=(“farm speciali*” and agricultur* and (“climate change” or “greenhouse gas*” or “global warming”)) OR TS=(“farm size*” and agricultur* and (“climate change” or “greenhouse gas*” or “global warming”)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-07-26	70	7
Nutrient flows	TS=(“farm struct*” and agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer))) OR TS=(“farm speciali*” and agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer))) OR TS=(“farm size*” and agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-07-26	45	5
Land use	TS=(“farm struct*” and agricultur* and (“forest cover” or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or “land use change”)) OR TS=(“farm speciali*” and agricultur* and (“forest cover” or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or “land use	2023-07-26	26	2

	change’’) OR TS=(“farm size*” and agricultur* and (“forest cover” or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or “land use change’’)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)			
Water use	TS=(“farm struct*” and agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or “blue water” or “surface water*”) NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use))) OR TS=(“farm speciali*” and agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or “blue water” or “surface water*”) NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use))) OR TS=(“farm size*” and agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or “blue water” or “surface water*”) NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-07-26	6	1
Chemical pollution (Novel entities)	TS=(“farm struct*” and agricultur* and (“chemical pollut*” or “novel entities” or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal’’)) OR TS=(“farm speciali*” and agricultur* and (“chemical pollut*” or “novel entities” or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal’’)) OR TS=(“farm size*” and agricultur* and (“chemical pollut*” or “novel entities” or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal’’)) AND WC=(Agriculture,	2023-07-26	36	1

	Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)			
Aerosol loading	TS=("farm struct*" and agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission))) OR TS=("farm speciali*" and agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission))) OR TS=("farm size*" and agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-07-27	3	1
Nutrition security	TS=("farm struct*" and agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*)) OR TS=("farm speciali*" and agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*)) OR TS=("farm size*" and agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-07-27	172	7
Health	TS=("farm struct*" and agricultur* and health) OR TS=("farm speciali*" and agricultur* and health) OR TS=("farm size*" and agricultur* and health) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR	2023-07-27	35	1

	Agricultural Economics & Policy)			
Social equity	TS=(“farm struct*” and agricultur* and (gender or (gender NEAR/2 equality) or educat* or literacy or “social equity”)) OR TS=(“farm speciali” and agricultur* and (gender or (gender NEAR/2 equality) or educat* or literacy or “social equity”)) OR TS=(“farm size*” and agricultur* and (gender or (gender NEAR/2 equality) or educat* or literacy or “social equity”)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-08-08	1	1
Economy	TS=(“farm struct*” and agricultur* and (energy or (sector* NEAR/2 (VAD or employment or wage*)))) OR TS=(“farm speciali*” and agricultur* and (energy or (sector* NEAR/2 (VAD or employment or wage*)))) OR TS=(“farm size*” and agricultur* and (energy or (sector* NEAR/2 (VAD or employment or wage*)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-08-08	31	3
Income & work: findings from here are used under social equity and farm resilience	TS=(“farm struct*” and agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work))) OR TS=(“farm speciali*” and agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work))) OR TS=(“farm size*” and agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-08-09	199	17

Farm resilience	TS=(“farm struct*” and agricultur* and resilien*) OR TS=(“farm speciali*” and agricultur* and resilien*) OR TS=(“farm size*” and agricultur* and resilien*) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-08-09	24	4
Total			696	55

8.4. Field Structural Change Search Queries and Results

	Full Search Query	Date of Last Search	Records found	Relevant Studies
Biodiversity	TS=((“field shape” or “parcel shape” or “patch shape”) and agricultur* and (biodiversity or (biodiversity NEAR/2 loss) or “genetic diversity” or “functional diversity” or “biosphere integrity” or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability))) OR TS=((“field size” or “parcel size”) and agricultur* and (biodiversity or (biodiversity NEAR/2 loss) or “genetic diversity” or “functional diversity” or “biosphere integrity” or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability))) OR TS=((“field structur*” or “parcel structur*”) agricultur* and (biodiversity or (biodiversity NEAR/2 loss) or “genetic diversity” or “functional diversity” or “biosphere integrity” or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability))) AND WC=(Agriculture,	2023-08-09	119	30

	Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)			
Climate	TS=((“field shape” or “parcel shape”) and agricultur* and (“climate change” or “greenhouse gas*” or “global warming”)) OR TS=((“field size” or “parcel size”) and agricultur* and (“climate change” or “greenhouse gas*” or “global warming”)) OR TS=((“field structur*” or “parcel structur*”) agricultur* and (“climate change” or “greenhouse gas*” or “global warming”)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-08-10	31	3
Nutrient flows	TS=((“field shape” or “parcel shape”) and agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer))) OR TS=((“field size” or “parcel size”) and agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer))) OR TS=((“field structur*” or “parcel structur*”) agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-08-11	23	7
Land use	TS=((“field shape” or “parcel shape”) and agricultur* and (“forest cover” or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or “land use change”)) OR TS=((“field size” or “parcel size”) and agricultur* and (“forest cover” or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or	2023-08-14	39	2

	deforestation or “land use change”) OR TS=(“field structur*” or “parcel structur*”) agricultur* and (“forest cover” or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or “land use change”) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)			
Water use	TS=(“field shape” or “parcel shape”) and agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or “blue water” or “surface water*”) NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use))) OR TS=(“field size” or “parcel size”) and agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or “blue water” or “surface water*”) NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use))) OR TS=(“field structur*” or “parcel structur*”) agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or “blue water” or “surface water*”) NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-08-14	5	1
Chemical pollution (Novel entities)	TS=(“field shape” or “parcel shape”) and agricultur* and (“chemical pollut*” or “novel entities” or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal”)) OR TS=(“field size” or “parcel size”) and agricultur* and (“chemical pollut*” or “novel entities” or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal”)) OR	2023-08-15	36	1

	TS=((“field structur*” or “parcel structur*”) agricultur* and (“chemical pollut*” or “novel entities” or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal”)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)			
Aerosol loading	TS=((“field shape” or “parcel shape”) and agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)))) OR TS=((“field size” or “parcel size”) and agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)))) OR TS=((“field structur*” or “parcel structur*”) agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-08-14	5	2
Nutrition security	TS=((“field shape” or “parcel shape”) and agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*)) OR TS=((“field size” or “parcel size”) and agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*)) OR TS=((“field structur*” or “parcel structur*”) agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-08-16	81	3
Health	TS=((“field shape” or “parcel shape”) and agricultur* and health) OR TS=((“field size” or “parcel size”) and	2023-08-15	11	5

	agricultur* and health) OR TS=((“field structur*” or “parcel structur*”) agricultur* and health) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)			
Social equity	TS=((“field shape” or “parcel shape”) and agricultur* and (gender or (gender NEAR/2 equality) or educat* or *literacy or “social equity”)) OR TS=((“field size” or “parcel size”) and agricultur* and (gender or (gender NEAR/2 equality) or educat* or *literacy or “social equity”)) OR TS=((“field structur*” or “parcel structur*”) agricultur* and (gender or (gender NEAR/2 equality) or educat* or *literacy or “social equity”)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-08- 15	0	0
Economy	TS=((“field shape” or “parcel shape”) and agricultur* and (energy or (sector* NEAR/2 (VAD or employment or wage*)))) OR TS=((“field size” or “parcel size”) and agricultur* and (energy or (sector* NEAR/2 (VAD or employment or wage*)))) OR TS=((“field structur*” or “parcel structur*”) agricultur* and (energy or (sector* NEAR/2 (VAD or employment or wage*)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)	2023-08- 16	0	0
Income & work: findings	TS=((“field shape” or “parcel shape”) and agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR	2023-08- 15	21	9

<p>from here are used under social equity and farm resilience</p>	<p>work))) OR TS=((“field size” or “parcel size”) and agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work))) OR TS=((“field structur*” or “parcel structur*”) agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>			
<p>Farm resilience</p>	<p>TS=((“field shape” or “parcel shape”) and agricultur* and resilien*) OR TS=((“field size” or “parcel size”) and agricultur* and resilien*) OR TS=((“field structur*” or “parcel structur*”) agricultur* and resilien*) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>	<p>2023-08-15</p>	<p>7</p>	<p>0</p>
<p>Total</p>			<p>378</p>	<p>63</p>

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